

NAVIGATING THROUGH THE STORM: EXPLORING THE CHALLENGES OF RURAL HEALTH MIDWIVES UNDER THE DEPARTMENT OF HEALTH'S DEPLOYMENT PROGRAM, PHILIPPINES

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 (Corona Virus 2019) Pandemic summoned Midwives to the frontlines. This phenomenological research explores the lived experiences of Midwives working in the Rural Health Midwife Placement Program of the Department of Health during the peak of the COVID-9 pandemic in the Philippines. Utilizing the Socio-Ecological Model foci namely; individual, interpersonal, organizational, community, and policy issues, the lived experiences were thematically analyzed. The challenges experienced include unstableness and a sense of insecurity owing to altered family dynamics, work-life balance dilemma causing anxiety and depression, dismayed over the deprivation of healthy work culture, embitterment over unsupportive Local Government Unit (LGU), and difficulties in implementing the protocols. The government should address the needs of Midwives, improve their working condition and strengthen the capacity of the community's key leaders to improve performance and promote general community health.

Keywords: *COVID 19 experiences of Midwives, challenges, Rural Health Midwives, pandemic*

INTRODUCTION

It was perplexing and terrifying when strict protocols were instated following the declaration that COVID-19 is a pandemic (Kumar & Nayar, 2021). Individuals were critically ill and dying. The medical staff faced several uncertainties, physical hardships, and psychological trauma. In April 2020, the Philippines recognized that the infection had

disseminated locally, and 24.7% of those sick were medical personnel (Haw et al., 2020). Despite stringent precautions, the infection rate continued to increase albeit the combined efforts of the major key players. Numerous researches contend that the rising infection rate and the uncertainties impacted the mental health of healthcare professionals (Kola et al., 2021).

Conversely, Midwives played a crucial role in rural health settings but were routinely unrecognized (ICHMD, 2020). In order to augment the current workforce of the Rural Health Units to provide care to disadvantaged communities, the DOH (Department of Health) launched the Rural Health Midwife Placement Program (RHMPP).

Government initiatives baffled the masses and met with criticism. Midwives were severely exhausted and misconstrued. With the dearth of study on the experiences of Midwives who joined in the RHMPP, it became a foreground that piqued our curiosity about discovering the real life experiences of the Midwives working for Rural Health Midwife Placement Program. This, therefore, aims to explore their lived experiences by looking into the entirety of their unique experiences.

Research Questions

The Grand Tour Question

What are the lived experiences of RHMPP midwives amidst the COVID-19 pandemic?

Sub questions

1. What are the challenges encountered by the rural midwives during the COVID-19 pandemic in dealing with:
 - 1.1. their own attitudes, beliefs, and knowledge of community midwifery work?
 - 1.2. their families, friends, and social networks?
 - 1.3. their respective institutions and organizations?
 - 1.4. their partner communities?
 - 1.5. policies in the national, provincial, and local communities?

METHODOLOGY

This qualitative study specifically used phenomenological research design. Qualitative research is aimed at exploring and elaborating the experiences of a particular group of individuals wherein, the process is often flexible and evolving (Kumar, 2011).

This method made use of frameworks to understand human experiences by exploring the underlying processes, their constructs, and their relationships in order to analyze experiences and identify emergent themes, patterns, concepts, insights, and understandings (Patton, 2002). As a result, the emergent themes were categorized in accordance with the theoretical lens and were connected to certain constructs (Suter, W. N. 2012).

The themes were organized according to how the participants conveyed their experiences. Consequently, each component of the utilized theoretical lens was aligned in conjunction with the significance or content of the experience, as stressed by the participants. Further, the enormity and grandeur of the developing themes were gauged by their voice tone, frequency in the sharing, emotions expressed through gestures and facial expressions, and the lucidity with which the incident was detailed and described.

RESULTS

Ten (10) Midwives took part in the study. The seven female participants were married, and the remaining three participants were two single males and one single female. All participants had an estimated family income of more than Php. 21, 000.00 monthly. All participants were employed for 4 to 6 years in the Rural Health Midwife Placement Program.

The table below show the emerging themes for challenges encountered by the participants based on its immensity and magnitude.

Table 1. Challenges Themes based on its Immensity and Magnitude

CATEGORY	LIGHT	MEDIUM	HEAVY
Intrapersonal		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exhaustion by overworked circumstance Difficulty in gaining an honorable image Loss of self-confidence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unstableness and insecurity in altered family dynamics
Interpersonal		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Infection dilemma causing people to be apart 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Work-life (family) imbalance dilemma causing anxiety and depression
Organizational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Compelled to undertake personal sacrifices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Disappointment over the poor government support Troubled by compromised DOH programs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dismayed over deprivation of healthy work culture
Community		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Struggle on the people's lack of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Embitterment over

	awareness of the importance of the COVID-19 vaccination	unsupportive Local Government Unit
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural and communication barriers 	
Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Altered policy on quality patient care 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulties in implementing the IATF (Inter-agency Task Force) protocol and guidelines

DISCUSSION

Intrapersonal Challenges: Unstableness and Insecurity in Altered Family Dynamics

Stable family dynamics, typified by a sense of contentment, healthy relationships, and the absence of a work-family balancing crisis, inspire community Midwives (Headey & Muffels, 2018). However, the indignation caused by the COVID-19 pandemic to the Midwives put their families through so much anguish changing their family dynamics especially their economic situation and relationship with their children. This is exemplified by a change from being an affectionate person to someone who is very much detached and consciously aloof – solitarily facing their battles. Many of them had to be isolated from their children and sleep outside of their house to prevent bringing the infection. They admitted that it's difficult, seeing their kids long for their attention and they were quite too young yet to understand the situation.

There were innumerable deficiencies in the Midwives' role performance and loneliness was evident. Their responsibilities in the family were affected, thus parents experienced a greater level of psychosocial problems especially those with children (Lateef, Alaggia, & Collin-Vézina, 2021). It is highlighted that married health workers and those with children face significant psychological and work stress during the pandemic (Chew et al., 2021).

Excessive tiredness has been linked to these changes in family dynamics. Nine out of ten participants notably expressed their exhaustion from several community health activities. This was aggravated by increased workload and extended working hours leaving them no time for mental and physical recuperation. This proves that the number of working hours affects work-life balance, indeed proving that there was greater work-life disparity with longer working hours (Ayar et al., 2022)

The attitude, belief, and knowledge of Midwives relating to self, family, work, and community are their inner predicaments. This made them contemplate their choice to be Midwives, some wanting to leave their sworn service. Despite the numerous problems

faced, their steady commitment to public healthcare service as a responsibility and passion were not shattered by health crises, thus, sustaining them in the service.

Interpersonal Challenges: Work-life (family) imbalance dilemma causing anxiety and depression

The work-life balance of health workers was negatively affected during the rise of the COVID-19 pandemic (Ayers et al., 2022). With the changes of their work-life synergy, healthcare professionals who are parents show an inevitable increase in stress and anxiety (Yayla & Eskici İlgin, 2021). This made the Midwives feel guilty about their unfulfilled family roles especially as parent to their small kids.

Midwives became anxious that infection might reach the household. They always hold guilt if one family member is infected and there is a contention that they are the source. COVID-19 pandemic exacerbated a Midwives' postpartum depression, leading to suicidal attempts and altered parenting. Thus, health personnel's concerns with COVID-19 infections had led to serious psychological anguish.

Social support is perceived as a crucial component of an individual's psychological well-being (Siegel & Dekel, 2022). However the COVID-19 infection dilemma separated people physically, compromising relationships with family and friends. They were reluctant to share time to express their affection towards their loved ones due to the possibility of spreading COVID infection.

Despite the COVID-19's frightening effect, Midwives believed that the pandemic crisis somehow unified families, friends, and colleagues. Midwives proven that relationships can still exist. Thanks goodness to the advancement of the information technology that amidst the distance and multiple difficulties, the pandemic somehow has brought people together (Kurniawaty et al., 2019).

Organizational Challenges: Dismayed over Deprivation for Healthy Work Culture

A positive work environment leads to an employee's satisfaction and increased productivity (Castillo, 2021). On the contrary, Midwives in the RHMPP believed that they were deprived of a healthy work culture during the COVID-19 pandemic. Midwives explicitly expressed how they placed themselves in danger by closely monitoring confirmed positive cases on home quarantine despite the lack of appropriate Personal Protective Equipment (PPE). They travel in the middle of the night to a far flung place to monitor patients and their contacts, putting themselves at risk.

The employment contract of Midwives in RHMPP does not commensurate with their actual entitlements based on the scope of their obligations. They were working more than the mandated number of hours per week consequently increasing their physical and psychological stress. Midwives while allegedly been underpaid, claims that their shifts exceeded eight (8) hours per day and even devoured their weekends, night offs, holidays and other personal time, without proper additional compensation.

Self-reported financial concerns have been linked to psychological stress. The strain is compounded by the Midwives' delayed pay under the DOH (for 2-3 months every first quarter of the year) and in general, their lack of job security, being job order employees. In terms of the compensation, RHMPP Midwives are entitled to a salary equivalent to the salary grade 11 (Php. 17, 099.00). Likewise, they are entitled to a representation allowance, additional compensation under the Magna Carta for Health Workers, and some amount for their continuing professional education. Commonly, they have a monthly gross pay of approximately Php. 25,000.00. Concerning this, Midwives felt that they were overworked yet underpaid, demoralized, and remained vulnerable in the face of the current pandemic, yet their salaries and other entitlements were usually delayed. Allowances promised to them by the national and the local government units were long overdue. They also expressed sadness that other health workers with similar workload and assignments, received more entitlements than them. Nevertheless, they expressed understanding of their employment status being job order employees. They are hoping that those who earned a Bachelor of Science (BS) Degree in Midwifery should have a higher compensation similar to other BS holder personnel in the DOH's Deployment Program.

Midwives are faced with a dilemma being job order employees, waiting for their temporary appointment, while many of them are finding other employment alternatives. They claimed to just persevere and remained optimistic, knowing that some of their previous colleagues were not given the same opportunity to be in the program again. Job uncertainty in both the public and private sectors is a perennial issue that adds to workers' stress. The Philippine healthcare professionals were among the group of workers deprived of a desirable environment during the surge of the pandemic adding up to their psychological anguish (Mendoza et al., 2021).

Issues on compromised DOH programs during the surge of the pandemic emerged as a subtheme. Several service targets for various health programs were not met because Midwives shifted focus from DOH program implementation to the COVID-19 control program. This resulted in an increased bulk of unfinished duties, especially the recording and reporting which are needed for the country's health statistics. The pandemic's "additional tasks," were on top of the regular functions that Midwives had to perform in the Barangay Health Stations (BHS), and these so-called additional functions were far more difficult and demanding.

The lack of support and insufficient funding from the LGU forced Midwives to spend their own money on health and health-related activities. These include, but are not limited to; finding transportation for patients, providing meals for clients on quarantines, purchasing medicines, acquiring PPE for self and patients, and equipping the BHS with necessary supplies, among other things.

Community Challenges: Embitterment over Unsupportive Local Government Unit

Through the local health board, the local government unit is expected to be proactively supportive to health programs and policies. Nevertheless, during the COVID-19 pandemic, demand for health-related assistance was relatively high. Eight out of ten municipalities in South Cotabato where the participating Midwives come from, were perceived to be unsupportive to the health programs during the pandemic spike. Midwives felt that community health is their sole responsibility. Consequently, Midwives, as primary implementers, were among the numerous public health practitioners subjected to community criticism of the government's response to the COVID-19. They admitted suffering of compassion fatigue as they poured all their efforts and personal resources to help people survive their health battles and yet, they were often unrecognized as “true” frontliners.

The dearth of logistical support from the local government unit to the rural Midwives added to their afflictions. There were cases of alleged mishandling of funds for COVID-19 management and control. Studies have shown that mental health of health workers during the pandemic was linked to the quality of organizational support. There have been indications that apposite support and effective communication protect healthcare personnel from having the poorest mental health outcomes (Brier et al., 2020).

The vaccination program against COVID-19 caused extra difficulties for rural Midwives. The community's inadequate knowledge about the vaccine's safety and benefits put the Midwives in danger. All ten (10) participants experienced having unfavorable interactions with their constituents in the Resbakuna COVID-19 vaccination program, owing to community social ostracization and lack of vaccine understanding. The difficulties experienced by the Midwives were also linked to cultural communication obstacles. It corroborated with the poll results from Social Weather Stations, which revealed a high level of community opposition to COVID-19 vaccines (Mendoza et al., 2021).

Policy Challenges: Difficulties in Implementing the IATF Protocols and Guidelines

As different LGUs issued varying memorandum orders, this caused confusion among the health team and the general population. As a result, the community's frontline of defense - the Midwives, were often the ones who took the brunt of the blame. The community's unwillingness to embrace the policy, combined with the implementers' inconsistencies, and the lack of IEC (Information, Education and Communication) and support from other key players, results in horrible experiences for Rural Midwives.

In particular, changes to the funeral policy in accordance with the Inter-agency Task Force (IATF) protocols resulted to some harassment of Midwives. Several other implementers of IATF guidelines faced unfavorable treatment from family members of a deceased victim who tested positive for COVID-19.

Conclusions

The COVID 19 pandemic significantly impacted Midwives, creating a multitude of challenges across various levels of the Socio-Ecological Model.

In the intrapersonal level, the pandemic disrupted midwives' family dynamics. The fear of transmission led them to become isolated from their loved ones, leading to feelings of loneliness and detachment. Increased workload led to exhaustion which challenged their ability to balance work and family life. These challenges led some midwives to contemplate leaving the profession despite their dedication to their duty.

Work-life imbalance is the main interpersonal challenge that aroused anxiety and depression among midwives. Concerns about infecting family members caused guilt and social distancing which consequently compromised the expected social support. However, technology facilitated communication and connection despite physical limitations.

Within the organization, midwives' felt inadequately supported. A lack of proper PPE exposed them to health risks. Underpayment, delayed salaries, and exceeding work hours without due compensation caused financial strain and demoralization. Additionally, DOH program implementation was disrupted due to pandemic's focus, increased workloads and led towards numerous unfinished tasks. The financial limitations of local government units (LGU) forced midwives to use personal resources for health activities.

In the community level, midwives perceived that there is a lack of support from LGU during the pandemic. They shouldered a significant burden in the community health programs while facing criticism for the government's response. Logistical shortcomings from LGUs added to their struggles. Vaccine hesitancy and cultural communication barriers posed further difficulties.

In the policy level, there were inconsistencies in the guidelines and varying protocols from different LGUs which caused confusion among health care workers and even the public. Midwives faced the burden of public frustration due to unclear policies and a lack of effective communication.

The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the need for better support systems for midwives. They require adequate resources, improved working conditions and recognition for crucial role in public health, especially during crises. Addressing these challenges is essential to ensure the well-being of midwives and the continued delivery of quality maternity care.

Recommendations

This study offers the following recommendations that may promote a healthy work environment for the Midwives:

1. Timely release of salaries and entitlements,
 2. Recognition of Midwives with bachelor's degree and the corresponding salary adjustment,
 3. Allow Midwives to enjoy weekends and holidays off,
 4. Ensure proper Midwife-to-population ratio at 1:5000 and 1:50 households for each Barangay Health Workers,
 5. Empower the community by training key leaders on Community Organizing and Community Development,
 6. Integrate respect on cultural diversity in the training of Midwives. Qualified Midwives who are organic to the community may be prioritized for hiring, and
 7. Conduct related study by triangulating the data to include other stakeholders, such as the supervising nurses, doctors, community leaders and the DOH. Certain quantitative studies proving the relevant statistics can be promising. A post pandemic study on Midwives' experiences will provide a perspective of their roles beyond the pandemic which will aid program review and prepare key players to future pandemics.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

Approval from the ethics review board was made prior to the actual data collection. This study adhered to the ethical norms and standards of research particularly in terms of ensuring rigor, respect to the participants of the study, storage of data, and dissemination of data and results.

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